

THE ROLE OF WORLD VIEW IN THE EDUCATION OF A PERFECT GENERATION

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Since the beginning of human society, raising a perfect generation has been an urgent task. Raising a mature generation is multifaceted. It should be a priority task to form a worldview, especially among young people. The worldview is introduced into the mind of a person from the outside, and it takes place from his heart by means of certain customs, rituals, ceremonies. In this sense, it has a social classification. Feeling the world and understanding the world has an individual character. On the basis of these worldviews, a way of thinking is formed, and a person accordingly determines the long-term direction of behavior and activity. Since the Constitution of Uzbekistan envisages the creation of a secular state, a scientific and philosophical outlook is formed during the educational process in kindergartens, schools, universities and other institutions.

The worldview of young people should be in a scientific and philosophical direction, and the religious worldview should develop within the interests of building a secular state in the republic. Because with the formation of a scientific-philosophical worldview, a unique obstacle appears in the way of religious extremism. Our current education system provides too much scientific information to young people. But in this process, the formation of a scientific and philosophical worldview, and the education of people of faith on this basis, should not be

overlooked. To become a qualified specialist, it is necessary to have almost all the information and knowledge related to a particular field.

Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and similar real human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything.

A student means, first of all, a seeker of knowledge. Therefore, the student's devotion to the country, selflessness, and patriotism are manifested in the desire for knowledge, the search for knowledge, the acquisition of knowledge, and the acquisition of knowledge. If the proverb "Don't put off today's work for tomorrow" is used in relation to science: "What if I complete this task tomorrow", "What if I read the book later", "I will clean my room another day, the sky will not fall to the ground", "I will learn a foreign language later, God's day is many"... this is the philosophy of a lazy person, self-deception.

If we look at history, the main indicator of perfection in any society is manifested in the attitude of a person to goodness, social happiness, humanistic ideas and practical activities based on them, that is, the criterion of perfection, which has a positive effect on the general development of society and human civilization, makes the society happy through the perfection of the individual. has been to do. Perfection in a person is, first of all, in his understanding of the freedom of thought, thinking and practical activity. In this sense, the call of the great Greek philosopher Socrates: "Know thyself" is also a call to understand one's lineage, the meaning of life, one's responsibility and obligation to future generations.

Social, political, economic, spiritual-organizational tasks for raising a perfect person in Uzbekistan are defined as the most important and priority direction of state policy because freedom and independence create the necessary conditions for the realization of the ideal of a perfect person.

Our head of state: "In the formation of a free person, we must educate free, well-rounded people who recognize their rights, rely on their own strength and capabilities, approach the events around them with an independent attitude, and at the

same time, see their personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country and the people." , they showed that this lesson imposes a high responsibility on every citizen and the mature generation.

We must not forget that raising a perfect person is a complex process. Unfortunately, we often have a one-sided attitude towards this responsible work. According to the teachings left by the wise, it is necessary to look not at the goal, but at the path leading to the goal. Most of us have decided to work based on the old adage that education is for education. There is an unsophisticated one who seeks to educate. But do the superficial lectures and long lectures we are reading have the desired effect? Does the continuous educational influence penetrate into the hearts of young people, or does inner-spiritual resistance arise, causing trainers to fall into an unfavorable situation? If we remember the words of President Islam Karimov, which are repeated many times on television: "...let's listen to the spiritual world of young people, let's try to understand their inner-spiritual world", it is not a conclusion that we have been careless and indifferent towards young people, that we have failed to educate them, but that we have forced them to educate them. The conclusion is that we thought little about understanding them, listening to their hearts. Due to our indifference and, at the same time, our excessive strictness, negative vices are forming in the nature of some young people: selfishness, hypocrisy, suspicion. The position of parents, teachers, and social institutions in the matter of education is incomparable. But we need to understand one thing: it is not possible to fully form the character of a perfect person with admonitions, speeches, lectures, but attitude and example serve to better realize the noble goal.

According to the great thinker Farobi, every perfect person is an example for others. With their wonderful qualities, sages influence the formation of the spirituality of others. An example is an important spiritual factor of social education. Such figures as Shiroq, Tomaris, Farobi, Ibn Sina, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur have thoroughly mastered the criteria of faith, loyalty, bravery, justice and love of knowledge, left a deep mark in world history, set an example for others, and

put forward profound ideas. With this in mind, our president I. A. Karimov: "Every person should compare his life with the exemplary life of the blessed ones, and ask whether I am a worthy successor of these scholars." They have left such a great legacy, let them evaluate their work with the feeling of what will be left of me", they put forward the idea that this should be a lesson for us.

Reforms in various fields carried out in our country - understanding of human identity, mature knowledge, broad worldview - are a big factor in our becoming specialists who have progressed in all aspects.

Every person begins to think about the meaning of life from a young age, tries to find his place in society, and accordingly his life plans and aspirations appear. The happiness and well-being of every person, family, nation, and the stability of our society depend in many ways on the correctness and humaneness of the beliefs and professions that people rely on, and how well this belief matches the noble goals and vital interests of their families, children, and people.

Young people are divided into material and spiritual interests, taking into account their vital interests and the satisfaction of their needs. Spiritual interests, in turn, are divided into political, spiritual, moral and other types.

The ideology of national independence should represent the future of this society, young people and their vital interests, and in general, it should be a source of energy for our people to achieve a safe, peaceful, prosperous and prosperous life.

As the state is the main reformer, large state social programs adopted by the initiative of our President serve to further expand the scope of good works in the direction of youth policy.

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